

D2.1 Battery Pack Functional Requirements and KPIs

Project ref. no.	Horizon 2020-LC-BAT-10-2020 GA No. 963540
Project title	Manufacturing and assembly of modular and reusable EV battery for environment-friendly and lightweight mobility
Duration of the project	2021 – 2024 (42 months)
WP/Task:	WP2
Document due Date:	30.04.2021
Actual date of delivery	14.05.2021
Leader of this deliverable	Eurecat
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Document status	Submitted

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 963540. This document reflects only MARBEL consortium view and neither the European Commission or any associated parties are responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Deliverable Information sheet

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
0	08/02/2021	Alberto Gómez	Creation of document
1	08/02/2021	Carlos Abomailek	Functional UFC Requirements
2	24/03/2021	Alberto Gómez	MARBEL Objectives and KPIs
3	30/03/2021	Lluís Trilla	Functional BMS Requirements
4	31/03/2021	Bernd Deibler	Functional Thermal Requirements
5	14/04/2021	Daniel Koch	Validation Requirements
6	15/04/2021	Luca Bertola	Functional Manufacturability Requirements
7	23/04/2021	Daniele Pullini	Functional requirements of the OEM
8	28/04/2021	Paul Gagneux	Technical requirements numbers
9	28/04/2021	Akash Kadechkar	Functional iSCM Requirements
10	30/04/2021	Alberto Gomez	Revised
11	14/05/2021	Eduard Piqueras	Revised

Executive summary

This deliverable includes:

- A definition of key performance indicators (KPIs) to be monitored during the project. To facilitate their understanding, they are split into different categories related to the expected impacts from the call and thus with the specific objectives of MARBEL project. When necessary, a calculation method is proposed.
- A definition of functional requirements to be considered for every subsystem within the project.

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List of abbreviations

<i>AI</i>	<i>Artificial Intelligence</i>
<i>BMS</i>	<i>Battery Management System</i>
<i>BP</i>	<i>Battery Pack</i>
<i>CSC</i>	<i>Cell Sensor Circuit</i>
<i>EIS</i>	<i>Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy</i>
<i>eVIL</i>	<i>Electric Vehicle-In-the-Loop</i>
<i>HPPC</i>	<i>Hybrid Pulse Power Characterization</i>
<i>iSCM</i>	<i>Integrated Smart Cell Manager</i>
<i>IMDS</i>	<i>International Material Data System (automobile)</i>
<i>KPI</i>	<i>Key Performance Indicator</i>
<i>MRL</i>	<i>Manufacturability Readiness Level</i>
<i>NPV</i>	<i>Net Present Value</i>
<i>SoC</i>	<i>State of Charge</i>
<i>TRL</i>	<i>Technology Readiness Level</i>
<i>UFC</i>	<i>Ultra-Fast Charging</i>
<i>WC</i>	<i>Wireless Communications</i>
<i>WLTC</i>	<i>Worldwide harmonized light Vehicles Test Cycle</i>
<i>WLTP</i>	<i>Worldwide Harmonised Light Vehicles Test Procedure</i>

Introduction

The objective of this deliverable is to establish a list, as exhaustive as possible, of objective criteria to check, make sure and evaluate how MARBEL project will achieve the expected impact using KPIs. A relevant list of Goals and KPIs, accompanied by their method for monitoring, is proposed.

On the other hand, to properly validate the MARBEL battery pack (BP) in terms of functionality it is necessary to divide the system in sub-system requirements to be matched during the project. For the whole system design, a battery unit of about 42 kWh and about 400 V will be designed and coupled in parallel/series with a second identical battery and a 400-800 V switch to match the around 84 kWh battery useable capacity of the Best-in-class vehicle chosen for comparison purposes (Audi e-Tron 55).

1. MARBEL GOALS AND KPIS

1.1. Readiness Level Improvement

MARBEL aims to reach an average Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of **7/8** with the new developments tested and demonstrated in operational environment, as well as a Manufacturability Readiness Level (MRL) of **7** with the capability to produce the system in a production representative environment, while ensuring maximized circularity readiness level and high-performance results.

MARBEL Pillar	Description of technology	Target	Means of verification
BATTERY PACK DESIGN			
TRL Battery Housing	New aluminium alloy with high amount of recycled material and topology optimization.	TRL 7	Demonstration in a complete BP at eVIL level
TRL Cell connections	Weldless electrical connections between cells.		
Advanced BMS functionalities: ultra-fast charging and thermal management			
TRL Ultra-Fast Charging (UFC)	Method for extrapolating single-cell UFC and thermal tests to full BP. Algorithm for UFC control based on battery temperature set and control. Method for designing high-voltage (up to 800 V) automotive charging systems. Solid-State technology. DC-BOX and Junction Box.	TRL7/8	Full system demonstrated with all subcomponents, UFC and thermal system evaluated at eVIL level
TRL Thermal Management	Aluminium foam as heat exchanger.		
TRL Battery Management System (BMS)	Flexible software, smart cell manager (SCM), secure Wireless Communication (WC) system.	TRL7/8	Full system demonstrated with BMS, SMC and WC integrated in BP and evaluated in eVIL
TRL Artificial Intelligence (AI)	AI-based expert system providing predictive early failure detection functionality.	TRL7	Advanced estimation algorithms verified with BP and integrated in eVIL
TRL 2nd life	Integration in 2nd life application.	TRL6/7	Applications tested in microgrid environment with scenarios technically relevant for industry
Manufacturing and testing processes			
MRL Process Manufacturing	Design for Assembly / Disassembly and remounting processes.	MRL7	Demonstration of Modules & BPs fully assembled and dismantled. Process optimised for production/dismantling rate.
TRL Validation	eVIL concept testing (real environment).	TRL7/8	eVIL completed

Table 1. List of expected Readiness Level Pillars and Targets in MARBEL project

1.2. Weight Reduction

Reducing the weight of the battery is a difficult challenge for the automotive sector. Since research on new cells generation with more energy density is not the scope of this project and since the weight of the cells is, on average, 56% of the total weight of the BP, MARBEL will optimize the mechanical and

structural elements of the battery system to reduce weight of the part of the BP not related to the cells (over the 44% of the remaining weight).

Expected Result	Weight Reduction (not related to cells) Goals
Housing. Optimized housing made by extruded recycled aluminium profiles. When replacing Steel with aluminium a weight reduction of 30% can be achieved.	3% Optimized topology 6% Recycled Aluminium replacing Steel
Electric distribution. With UFC based on 800V, the cross-section of the harnesses could be decreased by a 10%. Replacement of copper with aluminium for electrical distribution (bus bars). Aluminium bus bar has a cross section, for the same conductivity, 56% higher than copper and implies a 70% weight reduction compared to Copper.	3.6% Bus-bar cross-section reduction. Aluminium replacing Copper
Modules. Several components inside the modules can be reduced in terms of weight such as plastic parts without mechanical restrictions only for assembly. Foams for the separators and the cell housing will replace these parts.	5% Lightweight modules
Communications. Using wireless communication will reduce the wiring weight.	3% No communication wires
Thermal Management.	1% New cooling system

Table 2. List of expected Goals regarding weight reduction in MARBEL project

Using the information listed in the D2.3 “Modularity and dismantling guideline”, the weight of the different components of the battery will be monitored by measuring them and comparing the results with the average percentage of weight from other brands. Thus, the weight reduction will be always considered during the design phase and this will help to reach the objectives.

Brand	Screws (steel)	plastics	casing	other specific elements	EEE	Cells/modules	Total
1	8.1%	4.9%	15.0%	7.0%	6.5%	58.5%	100.0%
2	0.5%	6.2%	15.0%	7.0%	3.4%	68.0%	100.1%
3	1.1%	6.6%	16.8%	7.0%	4.0%	65.0%	100.5%
4	1.9%	8.4%	10.0%	10.0%	5.0%	64.3%	99.7%
5	1.9%	8.7%	18.0%	9.9%	3.8%	58.0%	100.2%
6	1.7%	12.0%	9.9%	13.4%	3.3%	60.0%	100.4%
7	1.6%	8.8%	10.4%	11.5%	2.5%	68.0%	102.8%
8	1.3%	7.0%	12.0%	6.0%	3.7%	70.5%	100.5%
9	0.6%	8.3%	13.0%	7.9%	2.1%	69.8%	101.8%
10	1.4%	7.7%	13.0%	8.0%	2.6%	68.0%	100.6%

Table 3. Weight information from D2.3 “Modularity and dismantling guideline” where 10 brands were analyzed.

MARBEL KPI	Unit	Description	Monitoring method
Power/Copper Cross-section	kW/mm ²	Measure of the power transmitted per copper cross-section	Current and voltage measure.
Standard components (screws, nuts, washers)	Kg	Total weight of the standard components	Weight measure.
Baseplate	Kg	Total weight of the baseplate	Weight measure.
Case	Kg	Total weight of the case	Weight measure.
Modules (without the cells)	Kg	Total weight of the modules without the cells	Weight measure.
BMS	Kg	Total weight of the BMS	Weight measure.
Electrical system	Kg	Total weight of the electrical system	Weight measure.
Cooling system	Kg	Total weight of the cooling system	Weight measure.
Other elements	Kg	Total weight of other elements	Weight measure.

Table 4. List of KPIs to monitor regarding weight reduction in MARBEL project

1.3. Extended Battery Life

MARBEL BP will achieve a useful life of 300,000km by applying an innovative thermal management system to cool battery cells more efficiently and to control sudden drop/rises in temperature of cells, modules, and BP. In addition, the smart BMS system developed in MARBEL will have a very accurate control on all cell states and balancing processes, thanks to the multiple sensors and the AI algorithm implementation. This will optimise the driving conditions and reduce all degradation mechanisms at the same time. Moreover, the UFC algorithm developed in MARBEL will work together with the thermal management system to ensure minimal degradation is occurring during the UFC process.

Expected Result	Battery Life Extension Goals
Advance BMS. Including active balancing, enhanced state estimation and predictive maintenance, minimizing degradation.	20,000 to 50,000 km
Thermal Management. Designed with aluminium foam technology to enhance the heat exchange capacity by 50% compared to the common cooling technology.	90,000 km
UFC. Reduced current with 400-to-800 V switch	30,000 km 2500 UFC cycles

Table 5. List of expected Goals regarding extended battery life in MARBEL project

MARBEL BP will be compared with the 95kWh (around 84 kWh useable) Audi e-Tron 55 BP. Although lifespan depends on how the battery is used and the conditions it is used in, Audi e-Tron battery come with a 160,000 km warranty.

Audi e-Tron 55 Specifications (95 kWh BP, around 84kWh useable)					
Range (Real)	Cold Weather	Mild Weather	Energy Consumption	Cold Weather	Mild Weather
City	350 km	495 km	City	239 Wh/km	169 Wh/km
Highway	255 km	315 km	Highway	328 Wh/km	265 Wh/km
Combined	300 km	395 km	Combined	279 Wh/km	212 Wh/km

WLTP Ratings	
Range	417 km
Rated Consumption	237 Wh/km
Vehicle Consumption	200 Wh/km

Cold Weather: Worst-case based on -10 °C and the use of heating

Mild Weather: Best-case based on 23 °C and no use of A/C

Rated: As published by manufacturer. Rated consumption and fuel equivalency include charging losses

Vehicle: Calculated battery energy consumption used by the EV for propulsion and on-board systems

Table 6. Audi e-Tron specifications regarding range and consumption [1]

MARBEL KPI	Unit	Description	Monitoring method
Vehicle range vs. cycles	Km/km-life	Evaluation of the driven distance per fully charge vehicle	A realistic driving cycle (WLTC) within the eVIL, adding simulated heating and cooling consumption with a climatic chamber and slow-medium charging for normal use plus a group of two consecutive fast charges to 80% SoC every 6.000 km and one fast charge to 80% SoC 2000km
Energy consumption (BP level)	Wh/km	Energy required for each km driven	A realistic driving cycle (WLTC) within the eVIL, adding simulated heating and cooling consumption with a climatic chamber and slow-medium charging for normal use plus a group of two consecutive fast charges to 80% SoC every 6.000 km and one fast charge to 80% SoC 2000km
Decrease in Energy capability (BP level)	%	Decrease of available energy (pack) with ageing	Calculated by the Smart BMS while aging
Decrease in Energy capability (cell level)	%	Decrease of available energy (cell) with ageing at different power demands	Current monitored and integrated over time (Coulomb Counting method) to determine the capacity in a different current-demanding scenarios and temperatures
Capacity fade (cell level)	%	Cell capacity decrease versus initial or nominal capacity	Current monitored and integrated over time (Coulomb Counting method) to determine the capacity for a particular rate and temperature while ageing
Increase internal resistance (cell level)	%	Decrease in power capabilities of the cell	Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) measurements or Hybrid Pulse Power Characterization (HPPC) tests while ageing

Table 7. List of KPIs to monitor regarding extended battery life in MARBEL project

1.4. Charging Time Reduction

MARBEL will achieve the BP recharging time reduction by implementing the “asymmetric thermal modulation” technology, which proposes to avoid battery ageing by controlling the thermal state of each cell of the battery pack. Hence, such technology requires of improved battery sensing technology enhanced with model-based simulations to effectively estimate the body-temperatures of each of the battery cells. To work towards more modular architectures, such sensing technologies will be connected wirelessly and managed from the BMS. To provide faster charge, the overall voltage level of the battery will be risen by means of a flexible junction box able to switch the battery pack from 400V to 800V

without requiring and undesirable conductor cross-section increase. Finally, the application of these technologies requires the review of the nowadays employed state algorithms. MARBEL BP will be compared with the Best-in-Class Audi e-Tron BP (around 84 kWh useable).

Expected Result	Charging Time Reduction Goals
UFC. Reduced current with 400-to-800 V switch	13.4% (4 min) Current decrease
UFC. Improvement BP sensing and UFC algorithms	11.6% (3.5 min) Charging efficiency

Table 8. List of expected Goals regarding charging time reduction in MARBEL project

Audi e-Tron 55 Specifications (95 kWh BP, around 84kWh useable)				
AC charging (0% - 100%)	Max. Power	Power	Time	Rate
Wall Plug	230V / 1x10A	2.3 kW	42h45min	8 km/h
1-phase 16A	230V / 1x16A	3.7 kW	26h45min	13 km/h
1-phase 32A	230V / 1x32A	7.4 kW	13h30min	26 km/h
3-phase 16A	400V / 3x16A	11 kW	9h00min	39 km/h
3-phase 32A	400V / 3x16A	11 kW*	9h00min	36 km/h
DC charging (10% - 80%)	Average Power	Time	Rate	
CCS 50 kW charger	50 kW	74 min	190 km/h	
CCS 150 kW charger	146 kW	25 min	580 km/h	

Table 9. Audi e-Tron 55 specifications regarding charging [1]. *Limited by on-board charger

MARBEL KPI	Unit	Description	Monitoring method
Cell capacity vs. UFC cycles	Ah	Decrease of cell capacity after UFC cycles	Capacity measurement
Charge temperature	°C	Cell temperature at the charging stage	Temperature measurement
Cooling temperature	°C	Cell temperature after UFC.	Temperature measurement
Increase internal resistance (cell level)	%	Decrease in power capabilities of the cell	Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) measurements or Hybrid Pulse Power Characterization (HPPC) tests while UFC
Charging power	kW	Power at which the BP is charged	Power-meter

Table 10. List of KPIs to monitor regarding charging time reduction in MARBEL project

1.5. Environmental and Economic Impact

Impact assessment and KPI definition in the MARBEL will, among technical objectives and perspective of developing battery solutions, the environmental and economic circumstances linked to the proposed BP in two ways:

- By proving to be a sustainable (environmentally and ecologically) and safe alternative to a battery useable capacity against a Best-in-class vehicle chosen (Audi e-Tron 55);
- By demonstrating the different improvements proposed in terms of weight reduction, extended battery life, charging time reduction, materials usage and finally, manufacturability, by an easing

(dis-) assembly processes and a better assignment and avoidance of unnecessary maintenance actions;

From this basis, KPIs dashboard selected have being based in the study scope under development on Task 8.1. Specific technologies to be analysed which consequently will set the baseline to be compared and a proposal of impact KPIs aligned with those technologies proposed and associated with project main achievements have being considered. As a result, tables below show a set of performance indicators categorized in terms of the main aspects related to the resource use, pollution emissions, toxicity risk and loss of biodiversity in the environmental sphere. Furthermore, for the economic perspective, it has been set technology expenditures (CAPEX and OPEX), total Annual savings thanks to dismantling and recovery of valuable materials into end of life as well as specific cost indicators to determine the feasibility of the proposed BP: Net present Value (NPV), Payback Time, etc. To that end, specifically relevant has being a state of the art performed in order to determine the key relevant issues to be considered along project performance as well as the main hotspots to be addressed during project development.

With all this global overview, list of impact indicators which jointly technical ones defined in the different sub-sections included in the present deliverable have derived in the mentioned dashboard finally selected:

MARBEL ENVIRONMENTAL KPIs		Unit	Description	Data required
Resource use	Abiotic depletion (elements)	kg Sb-eq	Increased extraction of resources leading to depletion of non-renewable mineral reserves	Foreground data related to main processes: Questionnaire preparation to be sent to the involved technical partners. Data such as material and energy consumption flows (input and outputs), declared emissions, by-products and products (primary data) will be demanded. Background data related to upstream and downstream processes: Data that include quantities of raw material extraction for the production of products, energy sources and end-of-life scenarios (secondary data) will be extracted from Ecolnvent database.
	Abiotic depletion (fossil)	MJ	Indicator of the depletion of natural fossil fuel resources	
	Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11-eq	Indicator of emissions to air that cause the destruction of the stratospheric ozone layer	
	Cumulative Energy Demand	MJ	Quantity of energy in MJ (net cal. value) per functional unit. Increased energy consumption from renewable and non-renewable energy sources	
Pollutant emissions	Acidification potential	kg SO ₂ -eq	Increased acidity of soil and water due to proton release from anthropogenic emissions	*Data from scientific and recognised
	Global Warming Potential	kg CO ₂ -eq	Increased radiative forcing due to the increase of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere	
	Photochemical ozone creation potential	kg ethene-eq	Indicator of emissions of gases that affect the creation of photochemical ozone in the lower atmosphere (smog) catalysed by sunlight.	
	Eutrophication potential	kg PO ₄ ³⁻ -eq	Increased biomass formation and loss of biodiversity due to release of nutrients	

MARBEL ENVIRONMENTAL KPIs		Unit	Description	Data required
	Particulate matter	kg PM2.5 eq	Particulate matter formation starts with an emission of NOx, NH3, SO2, or primary PM2.5 to the atmosphere, followed by atmospheric fate and chemistry in the air; NOx, NH3, and SO2 are transformed in air to secondary aerosols. Subsequently, PM2.5 can be inhaled by the human population, leading to an increased number of mortality cases and final damage to human health.	literature could be used.
Toxicity risk	Human toxicity potential – Cancer	1,4-DCB-eq	Impact on humans of carcinogenic substances emitted to the environment	
	Human toxicity potential – Non-Cancer	1,4-DCB-eq	Impact on humans of toxic substances emitted to the environment	
	Fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity	1,4-DCB-eq	Impact on freshwater organisms of toxic substances emitted to the environment	
	Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	1,4-DCB-eq/sup>	Impact on sea water organisms of toxic substances emitted to the environment	
	Terrestrial ecotoxicity	1,4-DCB-eq	Impact on land organisms of toxic substances emitted to the environment	
Biodiversity	Species loss potential	Sps*year	Potential loss of species due to activities performed	

Table 11. List of KPIs to monitor regarding environmental impact.

MARBEL ECONOMIC KPIs		Unit	Description	Data required
LCC	Life Cycle Cost	€/kWh	LCC as an economic indicator itself addressing the life cycle of the battery	Unit costs element/material/component/use/end-of-life
Infrastructure, product assembly and operation	Investment Cost	€/kWh	Total capital cost per unit of energy storage	Unit costs of element/material/component and cell production
	Total Annual Capital Cost	€/kW-year	Annualized value of total capital costs	Lifespan of materials/whole system
	Operation & Maintenance cost (O&M)	€/kWh	Total Operation & Maintenance cost	Input & output for operating cost associated with purchasing electricity required to charge the battery, and a charging device may need to be purchased. Data related replacement operations
	Total Annual O&M cost	€/year		Number of discharge cycles per year

MARBEL ECONOMIC KPIs		Unit	Description	Data required
	(including replacement operations)		Annualized value of Operation & Maintenance cost	Number of replacements per year (UF perspective)
				Replacement period
				Lifespan
				Overall efficiency of storage system
Use	Total Annual savings	€/year		Input & output energy in one cycle
				Discharge time
				Interest rate
				Number of discharge cycles per year
				Number of replacements (UF perspective)
				Replacement period
				Lifespan
				Overall efficiency of storage system
End of life	Disposal and recycling/reuse costs	€/kWh	Cost associated with disposal (landfill, incineration treatments) and/or recycling of materials and components and reuse of battery	Flow allocation between different materials in a EoL (regional/European) scenario
	Total Annual Disposal and recycling costs	€/kWh-year	Annualized cost associated to disposal and recycling	Increased extraction of resources leading to depletion of non-renewable mineral reserves
	Savings from recyclability	€/kWh	Only savings directly related to material recycling	Material recycling credits
Overall capitalization results	Net present Value (NPV) of MARBEL batteries	AD	Cashflow during different periods where discount rate is taken into consideration. Inflows/Savings and costs in the LCC	Lifespan of the batteries. Discount rate for European/regional statistics about future energy markets
	Payback Time of MARBEL batteries	Years	Calculation of the time needed for the payback of the extra initial costs	Cash flows of the system
				Interest rate
Electricity pricing	€/kWh	Cost of electricity acquisition having into account time horizon	Peak & Off-Peak electricity prices (Energy operators and official statistics)	

Table 12. List of KPIs to monitor regarding Cost

2. MARBEL Functional requirements

2.1. Requirements for eVIL charge

eVIL charge technical requirements are described in the following tables. As a way to develop such requirements, first the operations of the eVIL related with charging have been defined and following the functions to perform the previous have been established. Finally, a set of technical requirements have been set to allow “low-voltage” (400V) charge and ultra-fast charge.

2.1.1. Operational analysis of eVIL charge

Use-Case	INDEX	OPERATION	Actor	FUNCTI ONS	WPs	Code
UFC	O1	Perform ultra-fast charge	HUMAN	F1	3,4	O1- UFC
LVC	O2	Perform low-voltage charge	HUMAN	F1	3,4	O2- LVC

Table 13. Operational analysis of eVIL charge.

2.1.2. Functional analysis of Ultra-Fast Charging

Find hereafter the functions of the eVIL related, generally, with the charge of the vehicle and extensively to the ultra-fast charge of it.

USE CASE	ID	SYSTEM	Function	Code
UFC	F1	DCB	Vehicle detection	UFC-DCB-F1
UFC	F2	DCB	Charger identification	UFC-DCB-F2
UFC	F3	DCB	Cryptographic exchange of payment information	UFC-DCB-F3
UFC	F4	DCB	Allow charge	UFC-DCB-F4
UFC	F5	DCB	Filter DC-Power	UFC-DCB-F5
LVC	F6	DCB	Vehicle detection	LVC-DCB-F6
LVC	F7	DCB	Charger identification	LVC-DCB-F7
LVC	F8	DCB	Cryptographic exchange of payment information	LVC-DCB-F8
LVC	F9	DCB	Allow charge	LVC-DCB-F9
LVC	F10	DCB	Filter DC-Power	LVC-DCB-F10
UFC	F11	BMS	Drive JBOX contactors to perform 800V Charge	UFC-BMS-F11
UFC	F12	JB	Withstand current circulation for UFC levels	UFC-JB-F12
UFC	F13	PW	Withstand current circulation for UFC levels	UFC-PW-F13
UFC	F14	BMS	Balance Battery-packs to perform 400V parallel driving	UFC-BMS-F14
LVC	F15	BMS	Maintain SOX tracking	LVC-BMS-F15

USE CASE	ID	SYSTEM	Function	Code
UFC	F16	BMS	Maintain SOX tracking	UFC-BMS-F16
UFC	F17	BMS	Allow charge depending cell-temperature	UFC-BMS-F17
UFC	F18	CS	Cool the battery-pack to working conditions	UFC-CS-F18

Table 14. Functional Analysis of UFC

2.1.3. Technical Requirements of Ultra-Fast Charging

FUNCTI ON	INDEX	ELEMEN T	Requirement	CODE	PART NER	W P
UFC-DCB-F1	TR-1	ECU-DCB	The DCB should be able to detect the connection between the vehicle and the EVSE	UFC-DCB-F1-TR-1	FICOSA	3
UFC-DCB-F1	TR-2	ECU-DCB	The DCB should recognize the charger model and apply according communication standard.	UFC-DCB-F1-TR-2	FICOSA	3
UFC-DCB-F2	TR-3	ECU-DCB	The ECU shall support the different AC and DC charging systems: Combined Charging System (CCS) · system according to [IEC 61851-23] annex CC and [SAE J1772] ·	UFC-DCB-F2-TR-3	FICOSA	2
UFC-DCB-F4	TR-4	ECU-DCB	This ECU shall perform a immediate open in case of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unexpected lost connector: Proximity lost while connector is locked && Control Pilot is not connected • Unexpected unlock of cable detected by lock state (e.g. in case of manual emergency unlock) OR Any other conditions requiring immediate transition to the safe state necessary from supplier ISO26262 safety analysis to achieve target ASIL	UFC-DCB-F4-TR-4	FICOSA	3
UFC-DCB-F4	TR-5	ECU-DCB	The locking and unlocking mechanism shall be used for the charge coupler lock (CCL1+/CCL1-)	UFC-DCB-F4-TR-5	FICOSA	3
UFC-DCB-F4	TR-6	ECU-DCB	The DCB should be able to communicate with the BMS to receive BMS State-of-Charge digital signals	UFC-DCB-F4-TR-6	FICOSA	3
UFC-DCB-F4	TR-7	ECU-DCB	The DCB should be in charge f allow or disallow the charge.	UFC-DCB-F4-TR-7	FICOSA	3
LVC-DCB-F6	TR-8	ECU-DCB	The DCB should be able to detect the connection between the vehicle and the EVSE	LVC-DCB-F6-TR-8	FICOSA	3

FUNCTI ON	INDEX	ELEMEN T	Requirement	CODE	PART NER	W P
LVC- DCB-F6	TR-9	ECU- DCB	The DCB should recognize the charger model and apply according communication standard.	LVC-DCB- F6-TR-9	FICOSA	3
LVC- DCB-F7	TR-10	ECU- DCB	The ECU shall support the different AC and DC charging systems: Combined Charging System (CCS) · system according to [IEC 61851-23] annex CC and [SAE J1772] ·	LVC-DCB- F7-TR-10	FICOSA	3
LVC- DCB-F9	TR-11	ECU- DCB	This ECU shall perform a immediate open in case of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unexpected lost connector: Proximity lost while connector is locked && Control Pilot is not connected Unexpected unlock of cable detected by lock state (e.g. in case of manual emergency unlock) OR Any other conditions requiring immediate transition to the safe state necessary from supplier ISO26262 safety analysis to achieve target ASIL	LVC-DCB- F9-TR-11	FICOSA	3
LVC- DCB-F9	TR-12	ECU- DCB	The locking and unlocking mechanism shall be used for the charge coupler lock (CCL1+/CCL1-)	LVC-DCB- F9-TR-12	FICOSA	3
LVC- DCB-F9	TR-13	ECU- DCB	The DCB should be able to communicate with the BMS to receive BMS State-of-Charge digital signals	LVC-DCB- F9-TR-13	FICOSA	3
LVC- DCB-F9	TR-14	ECU- DCB	The DCB should be in charge f allow or disallow the charge.	LVC-DCB- F9-TR-14	FICOSA	3
UFC- DCB-F3	TR-15	ECU- DCB	The DCB should manage the payment information and carry out the payment with the EVSE	UFC-DCB- F3-TR-15	FICOSA	3
LVC- DCB-F8	TR-16	ECU- DCB	The DCB should manage the payment information and carry out the payment with the EVSE	LVC-DCB- F8-TR-16	FICOSA	3
UFC-JB- F12	TR-17	BMS	BMS should be able to swith the Junction-Box from 400V to 800V to enable UFC	UFC-JB- F12-TR-17	FICOSA	3
UFC-JB- F12	TR-18	PW	Power wiring should be dimensioned to withstand the thermal-stresses related with the performance of UFC	UFC-JB- F12-TR-18	FICOSA	3
UFC- BMS- F14	TR-19	BMS	BMS should perform battery-balancing of both battery-packs prior to reconnection in parallel in order to avoid current inrushes when reconnecting both batteries in parallel	UFC-BMS- F14-TR-19	FICOSA	4
LVC- BMS- F15	TR-20	BMS	BMS should maintain the tracking of the SOC of the battery in order to determine whether LVC should be performed. i.e. trying to charge once again a full battery	LVC-BMS- F15-TR-20	FICOSA	4

FUNCTI ON	INDEX	ELEMEN T	Requirement	CODE	PART NER	W P
UFC- BMS- F16	TR-21	BMS	BMS should maintain the tracking of the SOC of the battery in order to determine whether UFC should be performed. i.e. trying to charge once again a full battery	UFC-BMS- F16-TR-21	FICOSA	4
UFC- BMS- F17	TR-22	BMS	BMS should be able to impose the temperature cells necessary to perform UFC. Ideally in the approach proposed, to rise the temperature of the cells close to T=60°C in order to perform the UFC - short-time charge. To do so, the BMS should be performed either by using the Cell Manager or the Cooling system.	UFC-BMS- F17-TR-22	FICOSA	4
UFC-CS- F18	TR-23	CS	The cooling system should be dimensioned to maintain battery-pack temperatures during UFC within the range of temperatures defined in the definition of the UFC Strategy and during the charging-rest time	UFC-CS- F18-TR-23	FICOSA	3

Table 15. Functional Requirements for Ultra-Fast Charging

2.2. Requirements for Thermal Management

2.2.1. Functional requirements for the Thermal Management

Basic functional requirement for the battery thermal management is to ensure a temperature level of the battery between 20°C and 40°C. Temperatures lower than 20°C causes a faster aging of the battery cells and reduces the battery performance. Temperatures above 40°C must be avoided because of the risk of damages of battery cells and modules. The picture below gives an overview of the ideal thermal conditions of the battery.

Figure 1. Cell optimal operational temperature range

Hence, two main functional requirements for the battery conditioning are necessary for a robust and efficient operation:

1. Cooling of the battery:

The cooling of the battery is required in different operation modes and ambient conditions. Main operation modes are the discharging when driving the vehicle, the charging and ultra-fast-charging. The highest performance of the battery cooling system is required for the ultra-fast-charging. To realize this mode and to reduce charging times a predictive cooling mode needs to be investigated in the thermal control management. Additionally, the partial cooling of different modules to avoid hot spots in highly impacted areas of the batteries has to be taken under consideration.

2. Heating of the battery:

The heating of the battery is required under cold ambient conditions. The minimum temperature for operating a battery is above 10°C. All temperatures below have to be avoided because of damages of the battery cells. Hence, two different heating modes are important. During a cold start of a vehicle under cold ambient conditions the battery has to be heated smooth to get the appropriate temperature. This will be realized while operating the vehicle with lower performance on the one side and the heating of the battery with a PTC heater on the other side. After reaching the normal operation temperature the battery can be driven with full performance. The second heating function is the predictive heating under cold ambient conditions before driving. This can be realized only in connected mode of the vehicle to the external power supply. In this case the battery will be heated up via the PTC heater and self-heat up characteristics caused by the battery losses (battery limit specification $R_i(SOC,T)$). The heating modes of the battery will not request any partial heating of cells or modules. For ultra-fast charging mode under cold conditions (under 10°C) the battery has to be heated up smoothly until the appropriate temperature is reached. After reaching appr. 10°C full fast-charging performance is possible.

A third operating mode of the battery conditioning is the thermal balancing.

The dimensioning of the conditioning system in the battery is depending on several parameters which have to be considered:

The thermal mass and therefore the thermal inertia of the battery pack is important for the main dimensions of the conditioning elements, e. g. the necessary mass flow and inlet temperature of the cooling fluid. The thermal inertia of the battery will be considered also in the thermal controls to ensure a punctual or just in time cooling or heating function when required.

The mass flow of the coolant is depending on battery temperature and the inlet temperature of the coolant fluid. This dependency is shown in the picture below:

Figure 2. Example of requested coolant flow rate in function of the temperatures of the coolant and battery

An important input for the dimensioning is also:

- 1.) The geometry of the thermal channels in the modules or pack
- 2.) The principal layout and positioning of the conditioning device and package of the module and pack design.
- 3.) Thermal paths (R_{th}) of the heat transfer between the cell and the coolant.
- 4.) Number of cells and modules (dimensions and electro-thermal properties). Additionally, for the integration and dimensioning of the aluminium foam the parameters for overall weight and weight distribution are necessary.
- 5.) Average cell temperature (temperature sensors should evaluate the average cell temperature. Hence, the possibility of the positioning and also the numbers of temperature sensors for investigating the thermal behaviour on cell and module level are an important inputs and boundary conditions.)
- 6.) Maximum available heating performance of the PTC heating device.
- 7.) Conditions of the coolant fluid, possible maximum and minimum inlet temperatures, mass flow and chemical composition.
- 8.) Targets for ultra-fast charging (for example SOC10-->SOC80 in 30min).
- 9.) Battery limit specification (maximum voltage and current limitations for charging, ultra-fast charging and discharging regarding the thermal inertia and behaviour of the cell).
- 10.) The integration of the aluminium foam requests specific boundary conditions regarding geometrical package and dimensions depending on the used foam density and type.

2.2.2. Technical requirements for the Thermal Management

The requirements of the function thermal management (TM) for the thermal management system (TMS) are very depending on the cell features. A preliminary requirement list is proposed below:

FUNCT ION	INDEX	ELEMENT	Requirement	CODE	Responsible	WP
TM	TR-24	TMS	Heat rate dissipation during UFC (coolant @ 60°C) operation: 10kW .	TM-TR-24	IDIADA	3
TM	TR-25	TMS	Heat up time (passive, battery electric heating by joule effect) from 35°C to 60°C: 15min	TM-TR-25	IDIADA	3
TM	TR-26	TMS	Heat up time (active coolant @ 50°C) from 0°C to 35°C: 15min	TM-TR-26	IDIADA	3
TM	TR-27	TMS	Cooldown time (active coolant @ 20°C) from 50°C to 35°C: 20min	TM-TR-27	IDIADA	3
TM	TR-28	TMS	Dp cooling system @30 l/min < 0,5bar	TM-TR-28	IDIADA	3
TM	TR-29	TMS	Temperature homogeneity (different areas of the cell): DT<10°C	TM-TR-29	IDIADA	3

FUNCTION	INDEX	ELEMENT	Requirement	CODE	Responsible	WP
TM	TR-30	TMS	Temperature homogeneity (different areas of the module) DT<5°C	TM-TR-30	IDIADA	3
TM	TR-31	TMS	Temperature homogeneity (different areas of the battery pack): DT<5°C	TM-TR-31	IDIADA	3
TM	TR-32	TMS	Rth Cell=>Coolant: 0,5K/W	TM-TR-32	IDIADA	3
TM	TR-33	TMS	Rth pack level =>coolant: 1,5K/kW	TM-TR-33	IDIADA	3

Table 16. Functional Requirements for Thermal Management

2.3. Functional requirements for Manufacturability

The preliminary requirement list for functional requirements for manufacturability is proposed below:

FUNCTION	INDEX	ELEMENT	Requirement	CODE	Responsible	WP
DFA-GEN-F19	TR-34	GEN	The weight of all the components or sub-assembly that have to be installed or disassembled in the battery shall be less than the maximum weight that an operator can carry according the Standard ISO 11228	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-24	AVL-IT	6
DFA-GEN-F19	TR-35	GEN	All the components and/or pre-assembly subgroups that have to be installed in the battery shall have dimension less than the maximum dimension that an operator can carry according the Standard ISO 11228	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-25	AVL-IT	6
DFA-GEN-F19	TR-36	GEN	Manual insertion forces shall be limited to the maximum allowed in the Standard ISO 11228	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-26	AVL-IT	6
DFA-GEN-F19	TR-37	GEN	Manual tightening torque shall be limited to the maximum torque allowed in the Standard ISO 11228	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-27	AVL-IT	6
DFA-BP-F20	TR-38	BP	The design of the battery shall allow installation and dismounting of all the components without blind operations	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-28	AVL-IT	6
DFA-BP-F20	TR-39	BP	During installation and disassembly hand access and space shall be guaranteed in	DFA-GEN-	AVL-IT	6

FUNCTION	INDEX	ELEMENT	Requirement	CODE	Responsible	WP
			every area where manual operations are needed.	F19-TR-29		
DFA-BP-F21	TR-40	BP	For the positioning of the components physical alignment, positioning features and references are preferred	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-30	AVL-IT	6
DFA-BP-F21	TR-41	BP	The loading path for every component during the installation and dismounting shall be in vertical direction respect to the vehicle installation	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-31	AVL-IT	6
DFA-BP-F22	TR-42	BP	All fasteners ¹ direction shall be in the vertical direction respect to the installation to the vehicle. Remark: feasibility of different fastener directions shall be assessed case by case when needed for primary design functions.	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-32	AVL-IT	6
DFA-BP-F23	TR-43	BP	The component-to-component clearances during installation and dismounting in the battery shall guarantee no risk of touching and damaging neighbouring components. Remark: Minimum distance during the loading path of the component shall be 10 mm	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-33	AVL-IT	6
DFA-BP-F23	TR-44	BP	Component to component clearance in the battery shall be such to guarantee the tool accessibility for all the fixations. Remark: Recommended tool clearance is 5 mm. This distance does not cover clearance and creepage distances	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-34	AVL-IT	6
DFA-BP-F23	TR-45	BP	All the fixation points for all removable components during dismounting must be accessible by tools	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-35	AVL-IT	6
QbD-BP-F24	TR-46	BP	The design of the battery shall introduce features for easy and clear operations during installation and dismounting of the battery	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-36	AVL-IT	6
QbD-BP-F24	TR-47	BP	Design of the battery components shall prevent any installation	DFA-GEN-	AVL-IT	6

¹ Different fastener directions are accepted for primary design functions and feasibility of fastener directions shall be later assessed case by case.

FUNCTION	INDEX	ELEMENT	Requirement	CODE	Responsible	WP
			mistake during the assembly of the battery and if possible, give to the operator clear feedback about properly done operations	F19-TR-37		
QbD-GEN-F25	TR-48	GEN	Design solutions that allow automatized assembly and dismantling shall be introduced wherever possible Remark: Design for disassembly by automated or semi-automated processes to recover valuable electronics for reuse are preferred: e.g., fiducial marker printing; labelling, others	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-38	AVL-IT	6
DTC-BP-F26	TR-49	BP	A minimum number of different components type shall be used. Standardization of components shall be preferred.	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-39	AVL-IT	6
DTC-BP-F26	TR-50	BP	A minimum number of different fasteners type shall be used. A type is identified by geometrical characteristics, property class, diameter, pitch, length, surface coating and standard. Standardization of fastener types shall be preferred.	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-40	AVL-IT	6
DTC-BP-F27	TR-51	BP	The tightening procedure of same fasteners type, shall be specifically designed to fit the functional performance of the single joint. Wherever possible, in respect of the functionality, the tightening procedures of different joints shall be uniformized.	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-41	AVL-IT	6
DTC-BP-F28	TR-52	BM	Module dimension shall be standard Remark: deviation due to cell dimension are accepted	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-42	AVL-IT	6
DFM-GEN-F29	TR-53	GEN	The number of different materials shall be minimized. Recycled, recyclable and reusable materials shall take priority over other materials.	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-43	AVL-IT	6
DFA-BM-F30	TR-54	BM	Battery module assemblies of the HVBS shall be able to be removed, without mechanically or electrically compromising primary	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-44	AVL-IT	6

FUNCTION	INDEX	ELEMENT	Requirement	CODE	Responsible	WP
			design function, so that they may be salvaged, in their entirety.			
DFA-BM-F30	TR-55	BM	Electronic units shall not be integrated in the components and shall be easily removed and substituted Remark: CSC should be not integrated in the module to easy dismounting and reuse Interfaces of the electronic units (geometrical, electrical and physical) shall be standard	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-45	AVL-IT	6
DFA-CS-F31	TR-56	CS	The cooling system shall be designed in order to be easily emptied Remark: reduction of the risk to have liquid coolant during battery disassembly	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-46	AVL-IT	6
DFA-BP-F32	TR-57	BP	Sub-assembly groups that can be preassembled shall be introduced in order to decrease the number of operations during assembly/disassembly Remark: the design shall be focused to decrease the time and the number of the needed operations for assembly and disassembly	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-47	AVL-IT	6
DFA-BP-F32	TR-58	BP	The covers and removable parts shall be stand-alone parts. Remark: for easy removal and dismounting no component shall be mounted on the internal side of covers. If connections with covers and removable parts are needed all the connected components shall be installed on the exterior side and shall be easily accessible and removable before the covers and removable parts disassembly	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-48	AVL-IT	6
DFA-BP-F32	TR-59	BP	Each component of the battery shall be selected/designed in such way that once disassembled no damage appears on the component itself and/or on the system	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-49	AVL-IT	6
DFM-GEN-F33	TR-60	GEN	Liquid paste or sealing shall be avoided in order to ease the removal and dismounting.	DFA-GEN-	AVL-IT	6

FUNCTION	INDEX	ELEMENT	Requirement	CODE	Responsible	WP
			Removable pads or gaskets shall be the preferred solution	F19-TR-50		
DFM-GEN-F33	TR-61	GEN	Weldings between battery components are not allowed during assembly operations. Reversible joints are preferred Remark: possible exclusions could be cell to cell connections.	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-51	AVL-IT	6
DFM-GEN-F33	TR-62	GEN	Glued connections between battery components shall be limited to the minimum	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-52	AVL-IT	6
DFM-GEN-F34	TR-63	GEN	Every subgroup or components that can be replaced shall have a specific label with a QR code with all the info.	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-53	AVL-IT	6
DFM-GEN-F34	TR-64	GEN	Info needed for each component/subgroup shall be defined according to the standards and regulations.	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-54	AVL-IT	6
DFM-GEN-F34	TR-65	GEN	Labels shall contain all the safety recommendations and warnings as international standards.	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-55	AVL-IT	6
DFM-GEN-F35	TR-66	GEN	Every subgroup or components that can be replaced shall have a specific label (e.g., Barcode, QR Code) for traceability purposes	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-56	AVL-IT	6
DFM-GEN-F35	TR-67	GEN	All the info provided and linked with the labels and traceability systems shall be available for all the component lifetime including Battery dismounting, reuse, second life and recycling. Remark: The traceability shall follow the component lifetime (second life, reuse etc.) which could be independent from the system/battery lifetime	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-57	AVL-IT	6
DFM-GEN-F35	TR-68	GEN	All HVBS components shall have material identification markings, for all components, for ease of identification, for recycling purposes. Component marking shall comply with IMDS Standards.	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-58	AVL-IT	6

FUNCTION	INDEX	ELEMENT	Requirement	CODE	Responsible	WP
DFM-GEN-F36	TR-69	BP	Busbar to busbar and busbar to modules connections shall use unlosable screws ² .	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-59	AVL-IT	6
DFM-GEN-F36	TR-70	BP	If washer will be used in combination with fasteners, they shall be unlosable and part of the screw.	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-60	AVL-IT	6
DFM-GEN-F37	TR-71	GEN	Critical, toxic and/or forbidden materials shall be avoided. E.g., lead (soldering), chrome (paint), solvents, etc.	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-61	AVL-IT	6
DFM-GEN-F37	TR-72	GEN	Sharp edges on metal parts shall be avoided	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-62	AVL-IT	6
DFM-GEN-F37	TR-73	BP	Battery design shall ensure personnel and equipment safety during assembly and disassembly operations. Remark: process shall provide safety countermeasures when design solutions are not possible/appropriate. Remark: disassembly operations may follow dedicated protocol especially for batteries which undergo abusive conditions	DFA-GEN-F19-TR-63	AVL-IT	6

Table 17 Functional Requirements for manufacturability

2.4. Functional requirements for Battery Management System

The functional requirements for the BMS are summarized as follows:

FUNCTION	INDEX	ELEMENT	Requirement	CODE	Responsible	WP
Structural requirements						
BMS	TR-74	BMS	The BMS shall have a modular structure with three layers of governance	BMS-TR-01	PTS	WP4

² The unlosable screw is a technical solution that does not allow the screw to be lost in the battery pack during assembly and operation. It is not a property of the screws once tightened. In such a way the screw becomes part of the component itself.

FUNCTION	INDEX	ELEMENT	Requirement	CODE	Responsible	WP
BMS	TR-75	BMS	The BMS shall coordinate data flow among layers	BMS-TR-02	PTS	WP4
BMS	TR-76	BMS	The BMS will be able to operate with a number of cells in series between 1 and 200	BMS-TR-03	PTS	WP4
Power supply:						
BMS	TR-77	BMS	The BMS shall obtain power supply from an independent 12V or 24V source at higher level	BMS-TR-04	PTS	WP4
BMS	TR-78	BMS	The BMS shall obtain power supply from the modules at lower level	BMS-TR-05	PTS	WP4
Sensing						
BMS	TR-79	BMS	The BMS shall collect data from sensors at module and pack level, in particular current measurement shall be placed at pack level	BMS-TR-06	PTS	WP4
Communications:						
BMS	TR-80	BMS	The BMS shall collect data from cell sensors	BMS-TR-07	PTS	WP4
BMS	TR-81	BMS	The BMS will transfer data to higher levels of control and supervision	BMS-TR-08	PTS	WP4
BMS	TR-82	BMS	The BMS shall communicate towards outside the battery pack and vehicle	BMS-TR-09	PTS	WP4
BMS	TR-83	BMS	The BMS must encrypt the data generated	BMS-TR-10	PTS	WP4
BMS	TR-84	BMS	The BMS shall prevent unauthorized access and identify users	BMS-TR-11	PTS	WP4
BMS	TR-85	BMS	The BMS will communicate towards the charging and thermal management systems	BMS-TR-12	PTS	WP4
Computation:						
BMS	TR-86	BMS	The BMS shall provide accurate SoX estimations	BMS-TR-13	PTS	WP4

FUNCTIO N	INDEX	ELEMENT	Requirement	CODE	Respon sible	WP
BMS	TR-87	BMS	The BMS will be able to update firmware from external sources	BMS-TR-14	PTS	WP4
BMS	TR-88	BMS	The BMS must be able to execute the balancing algorithms	BMS-TR-15	PTS	WP4
Safety						
BMS	TR-89	BMS	The BMS must be able to trigger alarms and warnings	BMS-TR-16	PTS	WP4
BMS	TR-90	BMS	The BMS shall detect over-charging, over-discharging, over-voltage, under-voltage, over-current and over-temperature	BMS-TR-17	PTS	WP4
BMS	TR-91	BMS	The BMS must be able to trigger protections and disconnect the battery pack	BMS-TR-18	PTS	WP4

Table 18. Functional Requirements for BMS

2.4.1. BMS context diagram

The following figure represents the interdependency of several subsystems and interaction with users in the context of an Electric Vehicle.

Figure 3. Context diagram of subsystem relation regarding BMS and battery pack.

2.4.2. Functional requirements for the integrated Smart Cell Manager

The functional requirements of integrated Smart Cell Manager are summarized as follows:

FUNCTION	INDEX	ELEMENT	Requirement	CODE	Responsible	WP
BMS	TR-92	ISCM	The iSCM must measure voltage and temperature at cell level	ISCM-TR-01	OTC	WP4
BMS	TR-93	ISCM	The iSCM shall execute passive balancing	ISCM-TR-02	OTC	WP4
BMS	TR-94	ISCM	The iSCM must communicate bidirectionally with the BMS	ISCM-TR-03	OTC	WP4
BMS	TR-95	ISCM	The iSCM shall encrypt the transmitted data generated	ISCM-TR-04	OTC	WP4
BMS	TR-96	ISCM	The iSCM must obtain power supply from the cell itself	ISCM-TR-05	OTC	WP4
BMS	TR-97	ISCM	The iSCM shall withstand mechanical vibrations and temperature changes at the same level as the battery pack	ISCM-TR-06	OTC	WP4
BMS	TR-98	ISCM	The iSCM operation modes shall be: Deep Sleep, Sleep, Stand-By, Operation, Communication and Balancing	ISCM-TR-07	OTC	WP4
BMS	TR-99	ISCM	The iSCM must have the capability to stay in power down mode and wake up by external events or time wise	ISCM-TR-08	OTC	WP4

Table 19. Functional Requirements for ISCM

2.5. Functional requirements from the vehicle perspective

The functional requirements provided by the vehicle manufacture are related to the Vehicle Architecture (VA) connecting downstream the battery pack with the most significant appliance utility loads (Table 18, VA), and the battery pack Performance Requirements to supply a OEM's Vehicle of the segment benchmarked (provided in a full confidential version of the deliverable, PRV).

FUNCTION	INDEX	ELEMENT	Requirement	CODE	Responsible	WP
VA	TR-100	inverter front	Needed power to supply the front driveline: 270 kW peak 10s / 100 kW continuative.	VAL-TR-01	CRF	All

FUNCTION	INDEX	ELEMENT	Requirement	CODE	Responsible	WP
VA	TR-101	inverter rear	Needed power to supply the front driveline: 270 kW peak 10s / 100 kW continuative	VAL-TR-02	CRF	All
VA	TR-102	Auxiliary 1	Demand for Air Compressor: 9kW / 25 A (air conditioning)	VA-TR-03	CRF	All
VA	TR-103	Auxiliary 2	Power demand for the cockpit heating system: Heater: 10 kW / 36 A.	VA-TR-04	CRF	All
VA	TR-104	Auxiliary 3	DCDC converter for the APU recharger (Displays, signalling, the battery electronics BMS), 400/12: 5kW	VA-TR-05	CRF	All
VA	TR-105	Auxiliary 4	Charger AC: 22 kW / 32 A.	VA-TR-06	CRF	All
VA	TR-106	Auxiliary 5	Fast DC charging (current need) 150 kW / 400 V	VA-TR-07	CRF	All
VA	TR-107	Auxiliary 6	SuperFast DC charging (yet to come) 350 kW / 800 V	VA-TR-08	CRF	All

Table 20. Functional Requirements from the vehicle perspective

2.6. Requirements from testing/validation perspective

FUNCTION	INDEX	ELEMENT	Requirement	CODE	Responsible	WP
VAL	TR-108	VAL	The battery system must provide the connection space for a proper electrical connection, to fix cables up to a diameter of 240 mm ² .	VAL-TR-01	THI	7
VAL	TR-109	VAL	The battery system must communicate internal BMS data via an external interface (either wireless or cable-bound) 1.Communicated BMS-data must consist of at least the following information: single-cell voltages, temperature values for all points where sensors are available, full system voltage, internally measured current, SoC, state of relay connectors, error messages if existent, isolation resistance value/state 2.The communication protocol shall be according to the automotive standards (e.g. CAN-protocol). No proprietary protocol shall be used.	VAL-TR-02	THI	7
VAL	TR-110	VAL	The battery system must have a cooling connection either with direct connection of	VAL-TR-03	THI	7

FUNCTION	INDEX	ELEMENT	Requirement	CODE	Responsible	WP
			cooling pipes/hoses or with connector adapters, while for the latter option the counterparts must have a screw connection for cooling pipes/hoses.			
VAL	TR-111	VAL	If possible, a flow rate measurement shall be included into the system with a possibility to communicate the measured data to the test system via a communication protocol mentioned above (if not already included within the BMS dataset).	VAL-TR-04	THI	7
VAL	TR-112	VAL	The battery system must have a stable ground-plate to be able to position and fix the system properly during testing. It shall not only be fixable with a specific underground fixture.	VAL-TR-05	THI	7
VAL	TR-113	VAL	The battery system must show following information on the housing/case (e.g. directly written, or QR-code etc.): system voltage, system capacity, system energy, cell chemistry, cell configuration.	VAL-TR-06	THI	7
VAL	TR-114	VAL	The battery system must have at least four mechanical fixtures to strongly fix the system during testing (e.g. lashing eyes etc.) and to maneuver the system.	VAL-TR-07	THI	7
VAL	TR-115	VAL	Components, where it is possible that they are destroyed during testing and be replaced afterwards (e.g. fuses during short-circuit-tests) must be easily accessible.	VAL-TR-08	THI	7

Table 21. Functional Requirements for Testing/Validation

3. REFERENCES

[1] <https://ev-database.org/car/1092/Audi-e-tron-55-quattro>